

Using Artificial Neural Network for the Analysis of Air Conditioning System

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Abstract The objective of this research paper is to optimize length of a capillary tube in a split type air conditioning system in order to enhance the Coefficient of Performance (COP). We use mathematically acquired data for training and testing the, proposed, ANN method that is operated, at different input parameters. Using the mathematical data, for training, an ANN model is created based on Feed Forward Neural Network, used for nonlinear mapping between the input and the output parameters. We are using different activation functions and several rules to assess the percentage error between the desired and the predicted values. The optimization is determined by mathematical calculation, to evaluate COP of a split-type air conditioning system with 3 different sizes of capillary tubes. Assumed that, the experimental equipment was designed and constructed to verify the COP data obtained from the calculation. In our work we observe that the ANN model can predict the COP quite well with statically correlations such as Coefficient of Variance (COV), absolute fraction of variance (R^2), with very low root mean square errors (RMSE). This study shows that, as an alternative to classical modeling techniques, the ANN approach can be adapted to accurately predict the performance and COP of the Air Conditioning System. The results from the theoretical analysis show that the COP was changing in a direction contrary to the length of the capillary tube. When the capillary tube length is smaller, COP values tend to be higher.

Keywords— Artificial neural network (ANN), Capillary tube, Vapour Compression Refrigeration, Coefficient of performance (COP), Root Mean Square Errors (RMSE), absolute fraction of variance (R^2) and Coefficient of Variance (COV).

1. INTRODUCTION

The output of refrigeration or air-conditioning systems has been increasing rapidly in recent decades and refrigerationsystems become more important for people's daily lives. For example, room air conditioners used in China increased by about 15% per year in the past 10 years, and nowadays the use of air conditioners consumes a lot of electricity, amounting up to 40% of the total electricity consumption in the summer in some cities like Shanghai. Therefore, it is important to make the design process of refrigeration systems A simple vapour compression refrigeration system consists of mainly five components namely [6] compressor, condenser, expansion device, evaporator and a filter/drier. The following study is focused towards finding out the effect of the capillary tube on the performance of the refrigeration system.

The length of capillary tube mainly decides the evaporator and condenser pressure. Lesser the length higher is the evaporator pressure and vice versa. [4] The length of capillary tube may betheoretically optimized if the heat transfer

more efficient and the product performance better. Computer simulation is one of the valuable means to accomplish this target.

Air conditioning and refrigeration systems play an important role in industry, infrastructure and households. The industrial sector includes the food industry, textiles, chemicals, printing, transport and others. Infrastructure includes banks, restaurants, schools, hotels and recreational facilities. Therefore, the performance of the equipment is important for the operations associated with those activities.

conditions over evaporator and condenser and so the evaporation and condensation pressures are steady state. The accurate size of the capillary tube and its configuration can be predicted with the help of the conventional method, calculations, for the refrigeration effect, coefficient of performance (COP) of the system and mass flow rate of the system.

Though, conventional method is still used for designing refrigeration systems to determine the required performance, the actual performance obviously deviate from the required one because

there is no accurate model used in the design process. So, it is necessary to simulate the model to get actual real time results.

The computer simulation method has been used for designing refrigeration systems and has shown its advantages over the conventional one. Stability, Rapidness and Accuracy are the least requirements [1] for a simulation. These three requirements may conflict with each other, and then a compromise has to be made to achieve good results.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The blockage in the capillary tube results in lower injection of refrigerant into the evaporator, so there will be a loss in cooling. Typically, this problem can be solved by changing a new capillary tube. However, this also results in refrigerant being released from the system, which makes for higher cost and time wastage with low COP. Furthermore, the size of the replacement capillary tube must be the same and some sizes are difficult to source, which makes the problem more complex.

To come over these problems, the objective of this research is to determine the appropriate size of a new capillary tube mathematically that can replace the old blocked one, and by using the Artificial Neural Network (ANN), we can get the results which are very near to the real time operation.

3. METHODOLOGY

The conventional method, which involves the mathematical equations and calculations, gives the COP for different tube lengths, but as discussed it deviates from the actual result due to the many assumptions we have made to construct equation so, there will be many factors which effect when it comes to real time operation, to overcome that, in this paper we are taking the help of ANN to get more accurate results.

Firstly, we are calculating the COP for the different tube lengths with the use of mathematical equations, then these values are fed into the ANN to get the accurate results, the resulting values will give the optimized length of capillary tube. This can be done by comparing the mathematical values with ANN results with respect to the capillary tube length.

The specifications used in the ANN are as follows:

Network type: Feed – forward backpropagation

Training function: TRAINBR

Adaption learning function: LEARNGDM

Transfer function: TANSIG

With 2 layers and 10 neurons.

Fig. 1 Representation of AN Network

4. AIR CONDITIONING SYSTEM

Air conditioning is the process of altering the properties of air to more comfortable conditions, typically with the aim of distributing the conditioned air to an occupied space such as a building or a vehicle to improve thermal comfort and indoor air quality. In common use, an air conditioner is a device that removes heat from the air inside a building or vehicle, thus lowering the air temperature. The cooling is typically achieved through a *refrigeration cycle*, but sometimes evaporation or free cooling is used. The air conditioning system is basically the refrigeration system.

4.1 WORKING PRINCIPLE

A domestic refrigeration system is in complete compliance with the Clausius statement of the second law of thermodynamics. The Clausius statement simply states that a refrigeration system cannot operate unless its compressor is driven by an external power source, such as an electric motor [3]. In this case, the compressor leaves a trace in the surroundings by consuming some energy in the form of work by the electric motor so that to transfer heat from the colder body to a warmer one.

Fig. 3 P – h diagram of a refrigeration system

4.2 IMPORTANCE OF CAPILLARY TUBE

A capillary tube is a common expansion device used in small sized refrigeration and air conditioning systems. A capillary tube is a constant

area expansion device used in a vaporcompression refrigeration system located between the condenser and evaporator and whose function is to reduce the high pressure in the condenser to low pressure in the evaporator. Capillary tubes are extensively used where load is fairly constant due to its advantage such as cheap, reliable, simple to install, zero maintenance and requirement of a low starting torque to run the compressor.

By now, from above discussion, you should have acquainted with capillary tube and how they affect COP. Our research predicts the optimized length of capillary tube to give best performance.

4.3 ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK (ANN)

Artificial neural network is a computational paradigm that differs substantially from those based on the standard Von-Neumann architecture. ANN generally learn from experience rather than explicit program. ANN is inspired from structure of biological neural network and their way of solving problems. The philosophy of the ANN approach is some key ingredients from biology and out of those construct simple mathematical models that exhibit most of the above-mentioned features.

The set of measured values of the refrigeration parameters were used as target data for back propagation neural network training. Each training data set consisted of three input nodes and one output nodes. The performance of the neural network depends on the number of hidden layers and the number of nodes in the hidden layer. The structure of the network applied for predicting the performance was chosen by trial-and-error method. Training was done based on the back propagation algorithm coding. The architecture of the proposed four-layer network.

The above results are now compared with mathematical values and results are presented in the following graphs

5. MATHEMATICAL EQUATIONS

The system is assumed to work as an isentropic process and there are three different sizes of capillary tubes in this calculation.

Mass flow rate (m):

$$m = C_1 + C_2 \cdot T_{\text{evap}} + C_3 \cdot T_{\text{evap}}^2 + C_4 \cdot T_{\text{cond}} + C_5 \cdot T_{\text{cond}} + C_6 \cdot T_{\text{evap}} \cdot T_{\text{cond}} + C_7 \cdot T_{\text{evap}}^2 \cdot T_{\text{cond}} + C_8 \cdot T_{\text{evap}} \cdot T_{\text{cond}}^2 + C_9 \cdot T_{\text{evap}}^2 \cdot T_{\text{cond}}^2 \text{ -----(1)}$$

Where,

Flow rate(m) = mass flow rate (kg/h)

$C_i = \text{Constant, } i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 9$

$T_{\text{evap}} = \text{Temperature at evaporator (}^\circ\text{C)}$

$T_{\text{cond}} = \text{Temperature at condenser (}^\circ\text{C)}$

Substituting the mass flow rate data in the above equation we have:

From equation (1), we get the value of constants as:

$$C_1 = 117.7158$$

$$C_2 = 2.7149$$

$$C_3 = -0.2007$$

$$C_4 = -0.8751$$

$$C_5 = 8.5 \times 10^{-3}$$

$$C_6 = 0$$

$$C_7 = 0.0197$$

$$C_8 = 3.3866 \times 10^{-4}$$

$$C_9 = 3.1417 \times 10^{-4}$$

From the above constants, we can rewrite the equation (1) as:

$$m = 117.7158 + 2.7149 \cdot T_{\text{evap}} - 0.2007 \cdot T_{\text{evap}}^2 - 0.8751 \cdot T_{\text{cond}} + 8.5 \times 10^{-3} \cdot T_{\text{cond}} + 0.0197 \cdot T_{\text{evap}} \cdot T_{\text{cond}} + 3.3866 \times 10^{-4} \cdot T_{\text{evap}} \cdot T_{\text{cond}}^2 + 3.1417 \times 10^{-4} \cdot T_{\text{evap}}^2 \cdot T_{\text{cond}}^2$$

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 5 Regression plots from Neural Network

Mathematical models are typically used to model a system when the system is not so complicated, but when the complexity of a system is increased other methods should be used for modelling. ANN is typically used when the behaviour of system is the most complicated or the linguistic rules are needed to define the behaviour of a system. The main advantages of using Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) include, it can handle large amount of data sets, it has the ability to implicitly detect complex nonlinear relationships between dependent and independent variables, it has ability to detect all possible interactions between predictor variables, etc.

In this study we acknowledge that larger capillary tube decreases the tendency of refilling but offers less evaporator temperature while shorter capillary tube ensures higher cop initially but it deteriorates at a faster rate in lower temperature range by use of Neural Network, for vapor compression refrigeration system, models can be developed to predict the COP through ANN method. The best model is selected based on the best performance error for different network

Neural networks often exhibit patterns similar to those exhibited by humans. However, this is more of interest in cognitive sciences than for practical examples. These factors driven us to use the ANN, and after the number of epochs it started to give the values which are very close to the expected result with very minimal errors. Thus, ANN is very best approach to solve large data sets for optimal results.

The Regression plots, obtained from the Neural Network are presented in the Fig.5. From regression analysis graph it is clear that there is very minimal error, where the obtained results are the best fit to the system.

configurations. In addition, the models have been evaluated by means of the percentage deviation between the predicted values and the actual values.

7. CONCLUSION

This paper mainly focused on enhancing the performance of a refrigeration cycle (Air Conditioning System), to do so there are so many methods/ways, one of the effective ways (in terms

of cost with less ambiguity) is to alter the capillary tube length with suitable dimension which meets our criteria (high COP). The Artificial Neural Network (ANN) approach has been applied to vapor compression refrigeration system as an alternative to the classical approaches, which are usually complicated, require an enormous amount of the experimental data, and may yield inaccurate results. In order to gather the data for training and testing the proposed ANN method, Mathematical values have been tested for its performance at different capillary tube length with constant diameter. We used three different parameters, namely, *condenser temperature*, *evaporator temperature* and *capillary length* as input parameters and output target value as COP. The ANN model based on the backpropagation algorithm was created, the performance of ANN predictions was measured considering the three criteria's, Root mean square error (RMSE), Correlation coefficient (R^2), and Coefficient of variance (COV).

We used ANN to find %error between the theoretical model and simulated model, as ANN gives accurate results, our study found that %error was about **4.5%** and the optimized results are as follows:

FUTURE WORK

The above results are used in our further work, where we will discuss, how the COP of a refrigeration system can be affected by changing the *specifications* of the capillary tube. This paper focused on **ANN** method to test the model, where the same can be done and can also be simulated using **CFD** which we will be doing further.

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